

George W. Truett During WWII

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Few Baptist pastors in the twentieth century achieved the fame of George W. Truett of Texas. President Woodrow Wilson chose Truett as a chaplain in World War I, and the experience affected the Baptist Texan, most notably allowing him to minister in one of the most devastating conflicts in global history.

Truett was a proud supporter of religious freedom and democracy. A patriotic American, Truett never shied away from promoting self-government and the idea of independence. He faithfully served his nation's troops and allied forces, continually advancing the idea of democracy. Like most American evangelical preachers, he believed in the importance of religious freedom and, like most other leaders, thought it was justifiable to use military force to combat the evil of Nazism.

Truett felt strongly about these positions during the first World War, and continued to support them during the second global engagement. Religious liberty was an issue of great importance during World War II. While Germany sought to eliminate an entire religious and ethnic group, the Jews, as well as other religious minorities such as the Jehovah's Witnesses, Japan's imperial nation killed millions of innocent Christian citizens. Furthermore, the Japanese military destroyed churches, and Christians worldwide had to justify military action. Eventually, Truett

unwaveringly explained why military action against the Axis forces was necessary, just as he did during WWI. During the first war, he vehemently declared:

The sanctity of womanhood anywhere is worth dying for; the safety of childhood is worth dying for; the integrity of a man's country is worth dying for; the freedom and honor of a man's country are worth dying for. Very well—they are worth living for! Patriotism not only demands the sacrifice of life when the time comes, it demands the consecration of life, all the time. Every citizen is to live at the highest and best for his country all the time! In thought, in speech, in action, in service—we are to live, unceasingly, at the highest and best for our country.¹

Although the New Testament promotes peace, Truett believed God wanted leaders to protect nations needing assistance. How could one love “thy neighbor as themselves” and allow intentional slaughter to exist? Several evangelical Christians and many within the Southern Baptist Convention (SBC) viewed the premeditated onslaught against the Jews as an attack on Christianity. Truett led the First Baptist Church of Dallas to become one of the most prominent churches in the country, achieving record-breaking attendance during his ministry. But his position on democracy and religious liberty along with his fervent support for military action drew the attention of many Christians across America.

Beginning of the Conflict: Neutrality

Just as with World War I, the United States initially remained a neutral nation as war swept across Europe in the 1930s. Neutrality correlated to politics. English Prime Minister Winston Churchill constantly appealed to President Franklin D. Roosevelt for help, and while Roosevelt expressed regret privately and wished to do more, he was always focused on his political future. Americans were known as isolationists and preferred concentrating on their independence rather than participating in global affairs.

As Germany advanced, Europe was in ruins; France fell within a few short weeks. England prevailed as the last European power challenging Hitler and his quest for a restoration of a Germanic Empire. Churchill

kept his faith in the Americans and acknowledged in his renowned speeches that they had the power to shape the world's destiny. He famously said:

We shall fight in France and on the seas and oceans; we shall fight with growing confidence and growing strength in the air. We shall defend our island whatever the cost may be; we shall fight on beaches, landing grounds, in fields, in streets and on the hills. We shall never surrender and even if, which I do not for the moment believe, this island or a large part of it were subjugated and starving, then our empire beyond the seas, armed and guarded by the British Fleet, will carry on the struggle until in God's good time the New World with all its power and might, sets forth to the liberation and rescue of the Old.²

Undoubtedly, the reference to the "New World" referred to the United States of America. Canada was already in the conflict, supporting Great Britain from the beginning of the clash. But Churchill never questioned the American spirit, support, and eventual entrance into the war. While Roosevelt assisted in impressive means, including having Congress vote on the Lend-Lease Act, such efforts only postponed the inevitable: boots on the ground.

China, and eventually the Soviet Union, too, received assistance from the Lend-Lease Act. Nevertheless, Roosevelt persisted in his political ideology of neutrality for as long as he could. Great Britain and its British Commonwealth were the sole protector of western democracy. The Soviets and Chinese desperately defended their nations, losing millions of civilians and soldiers. The deciding factor of U.S. entrance came on December 7, 1941, when Japanese forces attacked U.S. naval divisions at Pearl Harbor. An intentional raid sought to destroy the Pacific fleet of naval cruisers and battleships. The Japanese action made Roosevelt's decision for him; America was now engaged in World War II. The President and Congress declared war on Japan on December 8, with Germany, Italy, and with Japan, declaring war on America in a chain of subsequent events.³

George Truett from 1939 to December 1941

In late 1939, nations knew Jews across Europe were suffering at the hands of Nazi Germany. Chinese civilians, including Christians, were also being killed in large numbers. While such devastation occurred, propaganda efforts from Germany and Japan attempted to diminish the atrocities committed. Sadly, such endeavors were largely successful. Even before the war officially began, George Truett recognized that the world was suffering. At the Baptist World Congress in July, 1939, Truett stated, "The astounding fact of ghastly persecutions, both racial and religious, continues to challenge the whole world with horror, and to make a blot that is an unspeakable disgrace to civilization."⁴ He later added, "Wars and rumors of wars even now are casting their dark shadows across the earth. All these conditions poignantly remind us how desperately we need help above ourselves."⁵ Being the exalted pastor he was, Truett pointed his audience to Jesus Christ for all of life's affairs. Christ could serve as the mediator and the ultimate prince of peace. He challenged the crowd:

Here then is the one all-sufficient Mediator between God and man, between man and man and between nation and nation. He is the Mighty Daysman, the Great Reconciler, the Creator of Unity. When men really love Him, they will love one another.

He added:

He was born a Jew, yet He belongs to all races. He was born in Bethlehem, yet He belongs to all countries. His challenging call is alike to Saxon, and Teuton, and Mongolian, and Slav, and Latin to come penitently to Him for His forgiving grace, and His empowering help.⁶

World War II underscored ethnic challenges and divisions across the globe. Japan and China were rivals—further, Hitler aimed for a German Empire ruled by an Aryan race. Truett's cry for unity and reconciliation highlighted the disputes of the day. Unfortunately, such peace did not occur, and the tension in Europe and Asia worsened.

At the 1940 SBC annual meeting Truett relayed concerns about the darkness dominating the world. He remarked, "As we look at sections of our world today, they are as unpromising as darkness and as ominous

as the grave. Violence and tyranny seem to be invincible. Sin and moral chaos appear to rule with unrelenting fury.”⁷ Truett argued for God’s continued presence in the world using an analogy between darkness to night and light to the morning. He challenged his fellow Baptists to acknowledge that the sun was shining somewhere in the world, and the morning displayed the beauty of nature and, most notably, the majesty of God. He declared, “One day war will be put under His feet, forever—may God hasten that day!”⁸ Living in anxiety did nothing but expel more fear and disappointment. By contrast, focusing on Jesus Christ daily highlighted peace and understanding. Ending his speech, Truett said, “Let us be done with the spirit of unfaith and defeatism and fear, this day and beyond, forever!”⁹

Before America entered the war, several factors played a role in the eventual attack at Pearl Harbor. First, Japan grew increasingly angry with the aid given to China by Congress and Roosevelt. However, the main issue was that Congress passed bills restricting trade with Japan, including fuel limitations. Prominent Southern Baptist Powhatan W. James urged for more aid to Great Britain and “advised discontinuation of supplies to Japan.”¹⁰ Interestingly, most Americans, including the editorial board of the *Biblical Recorder* publication of North Carolina, disagreed with James, again accentuating the popularity of neutrality.¹¹

Truett initially surprised his followers by not being as aggressive and vocal about U.S. military involvement as he had been during World War I. He was suffering from ill health at the time, but remained adamant that the U.S. had failed Europe by leaving the region after the First World War. At the beginning of the second conflict, his message focused more on reconciliation and salvation in Christ. Truett emphasized the importance of divine providence and speculated the war centered on sin and judgment. Truett thought God might be testing creation in a world where the spirit and flesh struggle in a daily battle. He preached:

I’ve wondered if, in the providence of God, he hasn’t allowed this great war to come down with its dark, desperate story and experience to come down; I have wondered if he hasn’t let it come on the world, that Christian people might see, “You can’t get on without me. You’ve tried to, and you’ve made a shipwreck of it. You can’t get on without me; you can’t get on without me.”¹²

Assuredly, the war made the souls of all people tremble. As in WWI, church attendance grew, as did Bible sales. In the summer of 1941, Truett addressed the topic of patriotism, guiding his congregation to a slightly different stance on the war. His teachings bore a likeness to some of his perspectives on the previous war. He argued, "Every citizen should be a true patriot. He should love his country and be intensely and unceasingly interested in her highest welfare."¹³ Truett discussed the history of America, including his past ancestors, and how they faced "darkness, tyranny and defeated oppression."¹⁴ He highlighted the need to face darkness in the name of Christ, underlining the same message he used during WWI:

Patriotism not only demands the sacrifice of life when the time comes, it demands the consecration of life, all the time. Every citizen is to live at the highest and best for his country all the time! In thought, in speech, in action, in service—we are to live, unceasingly, at the highest and best for our country.¹⁵

Truett used the greatest commandment of Jesus to prove that one could not sit idly by and do nothing when their "neighbor" needed help. Every believer had the duty to supply aid, partake in mission work, and potentially face tyranny in the name of Christ.¹⁶ Later, he explained only righteousness could overcome darkness. He stated, "We must remember all the time, you can't have peace until first of all you have righteousness. Unrighteousness must be called to account. The forces of unrighteousness must be challenged. Lawlessness must be called to requisition. Lawlessness must be confronted by law and order."¹⁷ During the 1941 annual gathering of the Baptist General Convention of Texas, which Truett attended and made several remarks, the opening address underscored a need to face darkness. President A. D. Foreman declared:

We cannot face the adversaries of righteousness in this critical hour by taking the road of least resistance, nor by yielding to the siren call of indifference and complacency. Neither can we afford to lend one word of encouragement to a spirit of defeatism. Baptists can make no progress nor can they exist in a state of believe nothing, do nothing, and be nothing. Ours is a militant religion, and we are privileged to avail ourselves of the armor that speaks of battle and

victory. It is true that we are not authorized to reform the world nor force our religion upon others, but we are set to the task of winning lost humanity to Christ, to a spiritual Kingdom of righteousness that assures freedom here, and eternal life hereafter.¹⁸

The speech, given just a month before the attack at Pearl Harbor, give insight into the day's mood. While America had not entered the conflict, the atmosphere across the country slowly changed.

At the 1941 SBC annual meeting, daily meetings focused on missionary assistance. A year prior, an "emergency committee" had been formed, underscoring the turmoil of the present day. Proudly asserting his denomination's reputation, Truett concluded, "We believe that the response to this emergency appeal has deepened the missionary zeal of our people and that our gifts to this vitally important cause will further commit our people to every cause fostered by our beloved denomination."¹⁹ Southern Baptists, historically known to evangelize and partake in the Great Commission, played a significant role in providing aid whenever and wherever needed. Such support undoubtedly took an entirely different meaning following admission into the war. As North America's largest denomination, SBC members soon geared up for duty.

1941 to 1944

Upon hearing the news of the attack at Pearl Harbor, Truett declared, "God help us all."²⁰ Keith Durso has shared that Truett wrote in his diary, "May His will be done, in all the lessons and outcome of the awful conflict!"²¹ America now entered the deadliest war in mankind's history, sending troops to fight for the principle Truett so earnestly held close to his heart: democracy. Following the attack, he commented, "As we face the tragic situation that now confronts the world, it behooves us to remember that certain collateral blessings may be had and are being had out of the desperate situation which we are being called to pass."²² He added:

A great fire is often followed by repairments and renovations and improvements and better conditions for the people. And so is it with a great flood; time and time again, the great flood—carrying destruction to both life and property—has been followed by improvements and safeguards for the people to follow in the wake of such a disaster.

A great epidemic of sickness is often the occasion for the most painstaking and thoughtful and careful preparation that such epidemics shall not occur again, or if they do, shall be abated, shall be greatly reduced by what scientific, and other preparations may make against such visitations. Even so, a war—cruel and inhuman, merciless and bloody as it may be—may often be attended by certain collateral blessings, which you would do well to remember.²³

In the subsequent weeks, months, and years, America sent thousands of troops to Europe and the Pacific. Truett sought to be a voice of reason in the midst of death and darkness, and show that understanding and peace could still be found. He knew well the horrors of war; he saw firsthand the destruction of human life during his time in WWI and perhaps remained the best preacher to shepherd his church on such matters. In one sermon, he brought attention to the concept of liberty, which he asserted was at stake. He further argued that Americans needed to ensure their nation played the role of the protector. Similar to his ministry during the First World War, Truett did everything possible to assist young men heading off to war. Durso writes:

FBC (First Baptist Church) ministered to soldiers in the Dallas area. It provided a Soldier Center, a large lounge/reading area, where soldiers could relax and feel at home. When the ministry expanded, the church hired Mrs. E. E. Partain to direct the center. The church also placed cots in the basement rooms of FBC's Sunday school building for soldiers on leave who could not find lodging in Dallas.²⁴

Although Truett supported his troops and took a stance on the new engagement, he also criticized America and its lack of involvement following WWI. Truett mentioned, "Smaller nations were vulnerable and needed the U.S. for support, protection, and guidance."²⁵ He shared:

I must say as a moral and religious teacher that it is my deep conviction that our nation made years ago and continued to make one of the most colossal blunders in the history of mankind when our nation put her skirts about her, wrapped her robe more tightly, and withdrew from any participation in or cooperation with the great movement known as the League of Nations.²⁶

While he maintained his criticism of the nation's lack of involvement following the World War I, Truett also knew the country needed to focus on the future: "We are under God, we're under His authority, we're under His dominion, we're under His guidance and government, and He governs by great principles of righteousness."²⁷ Perhaps best known for his regular use of the phrase *Thy will be done*, Truett vigorously adhered to the concept of divine providence or the idea that God's will affected all aspects of life and world affairs.

In late April of 1942 Truett gave a speech in Raleigh, North Carolina. The *Biblical Recorder* reported that Truett strongly supported the war and believed religious freedom was at risk. Isolationism did not help America but made the nation more "vulnerable."²⁸ Truett asserted that American politicians put the world in danger, including millions of citizens.²⁹ Further, the mere existence of religious liberty, including Christianity, was at stake. The column read:

The urgent question of this hour is not whether people will be Baptists or Methodists, but whether they will be Christians or pagans. The real battle is between Christianity and paganism: And if Christians are to stem the awful tide of paganism sweeping the world, it will be essential and imperative that all Christian groups shall join hands and hearts in the Herculean task.³⁰

The war constantly challenged Americans to self-reflect on the purpose of life, salvation, and the reality of darkness. The Christian message of deliverance and redemption easily answered religious and philosophical questions. Truett's chief aim always centered on preaching the gospel to the lost and confronting the world's ways, which brought only disappointment. Imagine a world where righteousness prevailed and sin faced Christ's light. He preached:

The self-centered nation is lost, and there are nations now on the toboggan slide because they're marked for doom. History will not let us forget that nations and cities, once proud and powerful, who forgot God, now sleep in the cemetery of defeated peoples because they forgot God. The self-centered city, the self-centered denomination, the self-centered local church, the self-centered family, the self-centered individual, man or woman, is going down the toboggan and is marked for defeat and doom.³¹

In both world wars, Truett distinctively urged his audience to consider *Christ or Chaos*. Of course, chaos led only to heartbreak, destruction, and war. In contrast, Christ delivered peace, understanding, and salvation. Truett knew the foundation of any negotiation needed to emphasize the Lordship of Christ and underscore His teachings. In another sermon, he said:

We must find a way to end war, and our boys and girls going away now, to defend our country—as I think they ought to do—it's a defensive war we're waging. We're not out for anybody's land, we're not out for anybody's territory, we're not out for anybody's lust of gold: we're out for the defense of our homes, and civil government is ordained of God and every man and woman should be the best citizen possible, throwing off never on the great duties of citizenship.³²

Like so many Christians before him, Truett defended his nation's involvement in war as a “defense” of one's land. Assuredly, the goal was for the fight to end and peace to prevail. With his strong patriotic background, Truett constantly taught the war must be won.

Even in times of war, Truett urged his congregation to display biblical attributes such as forgiveness and consistently seek to maintain peace. While acknowledging that, in his eyes, democracy was battling tyranny, he nevertheless highlighted the importance of a godly spirit, “No matter what we have undergone and suffered, we must try to forgive those who injure us, and remember only the lesson gained thereby. Christ taught us to hate the evil in men, but not men themselves.”³³ Thankfulness and servitude also underscored the Christian spirit. Here, Truett taught, “At this season, our hearts go out in untold gratitude and most fervent prayers for our grandly heroic men and women in the armed service of their country.”³⁴ Between 1943 and 1944, Truett seldom preached, even writing a resignation letter to his beloved church. Truett's health worsened, and those in his private circle felt his time was ending. Still, Truett voiced his opinions, and was often invited to private events and conferences.

The Death of George W. Truett

Becoming sick a year earlier in 1943, Truett never fully healed and continued to struggle. The SBC decided to air George Truett's sermons on the airwaves for the upcoming months. Truett's teachings were well received and in high demand for people nationwide.³⁵ Two days after the release of his sermons, he passed away. Executive Secretary of Education for the SBC, Joe Burton, shared his last moments with Truett. Burton met with him weeks before his passing and explained that Truett's "faith was strong in his last days on earth."³⁶ Truett asked, "Burton to pray with him, and specifically, pray that he [Truett] would be entirely submissive to the will of God."³⁷ J.H. Rushbrooke, President of the Baptist World Alliance, shared the following of Truett: "His interest in missions was rooted in his sense of the all importance of Christ for the individual everywhere, and this sense was born of his own experience."³⁸ Burton wrote the following, "The secret of his great life and of his world-girdling ministry was his surrender to the will of God."³⁹ The *Fort Worth Star-Telegram* too announced his death:

Dr. George W. Truett, who died Friday night at his home, was an international figure in the Baptist denomination, which signally honored him by electing him unanimously to the presidency of the Baptist World Alliance in Berlin in 1934.⁴⁰

Adding:

Dr. Truett was aptly described as one of the outstanding preachers in American history, and in that role he presented simply the good news of Christianity as a message tangible to all people because Dr. Truett himself had been imbued with faith in what he preached. The great influence of Dr. Truett was not attributable alone to his ability as a speaker and leader but primarily to the fact that he lived the beliefs he espoused. In that respect, he gave an inspiring example to those who knew him, and his influence had a profound effect upon the lives of others, including many outside of the denomination.⁴¹

While Truett would no longer be with Americans on Earth, thousands of people continued to hear his sermons over the airwaves.

Baptists worldwide lost a leader of their faith in George W. Truett. His funeral in Dallas became the most widely attended service in the city's history.

W. A. Criswell ultimately took the pulpit and created his own legacy, surrounded by the message of Jesus Christ. The war continued, ending in 1945 with an American victory. Truett, a patriotic American, would have rejoiced over the end of the conflict and his country's ultimate victory.

The study of warfare highlights the darkness of humanity. It also underscores the love of Christ and the duty of believers worldwide called as Christians to engage in missionary and evangelism efforts. While the imperialist nations of Japan and Nazi Germany were defeated, tyranny came knocking almost as soon as the war ended. The United States never again became a nation of isolationism yet faced darkness again with longstanding conflicts against communism—a political ideology of darkness that is in opposition to the very tenets of Christianity. Truett's message of peace, liberty, and salvation still applies today. His pastoral legacy continues, as does his patriotic service and message during both world wars.

Conclusion

George W. Truett—named after the first President of the United States—was a proud and patriotic American. When called to serve his nation in WWI, he volunteered his time and risked his life to spread the gospel to soldiers in Europe. During WWII, the pastor in his seventies preached the same message, always focused on the will and saving power of Christ. The message was relatively simple yet challenging to resolve in a fallen world, although it always focused on heaven, Jesus Christ, and righteousness.

Truett was vocal about criticizing American politicians for their post-World War I failures and believed America had a responsibility to serve the world during World War II. He supported the war efforts and maintained that the U.S. must achieve victory for Christianity to remain in such a fallen world. Rightfully so, religious liberty was in jeopardy, and here, Truett knew his nation could free the globe from tyranny. When Truett preached, wrote, or delivered a speech, his audience listened. This remained clear during his entire ministry. Secular newspapers, too,

adored the pastor and gave constant acclamations for his service, preaching, and ministry. He believed in being an American patriot and felt that his nation was unique globally, convinced it was founded on Christian principles. As a staunch Baptist, he encouraged his audience to always focus on Heaven and Jesus Christ while also being able to worship freely. For George Truett, religious liberty was worth fighting and dying for.

Notes

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11 *Ibid.*

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